

IMPROVING YOUTH LEGAL LITERACY AS AN IMPORTANT PEDAGOGICAL TOOL IN CREATING CRIMINOLOGY STABILITY AMONG JUVENILE

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ABSTRACT

This article contains scientific analyzes and suggestions on control and prevention of delinquency among minors. In the article, together with the suggestions and recommendations of foreign experts regarding the prevention of crime among young people, national experience, age-old traditions, including the prevention of the increase in crime among young people, the increase of criminal security, the creation of a stable criminal situation among young people, family and neighborhood and suggestions and recommendations are given regarding the activity of preventive control bodies.

Introduction: Ensuring human rights and freedoms is considered the highest value, not only increases citizens' love for their motherland and their positive efforts for the future of the country, but also pride in the concepts of nation and homeland. and increases feelings of pride. Human rights are guaranteed by various legal norms (women's rights, disabled people's rights, prisoners' rights, patients' rights) by influential countries and organizations of the world. Under the influence of several thousand years of historical processes, the "Children's rights" section, which is a specific section of human rights, was formed. There is a United Nations convention on the same issue, Article 1 of which states that "Every human being under the age of 18 years is, under the law applicable to a child, unless he or she has attained puberty prematurely." is defined as".

Uzbekistan Children in the Republic the right and freedoms according to national legislation and computers there is That's it with together , Uzbekistan The Republic is the same in the matter generally accepted reached in conventions participation is enough That's it with together this convention decisions our country in the area national tradition and from traditions , national to himself characteristic come came out without current is enough Subject on the surface national to legislation look throwing if so, this about our country century experience, to himself special knowledge and malaksi that there is witness to be can. For example , in 1991 " To the youth about state about policy the law acceptance to be done , Main our dictionary " Uzbekistan Republic state It is also mentioned in the Constitution the process strong determined laying , modernization in the course of " To the youth about state about policy of the law new in editing acceptance to be carried out , in our country in 2008 "

Youth year ", 2010 year " Barkamol generation year " in our country our future foundation was - to young people attention big that showing stands.

Main part : Subject on the surface to compare and to compare in order to, foreign studies comment cause transition to the goal is appropriate. Plotnikov AD, Davitnidze IL, Jerugov RT, Kozlov AA in research to young people attention the future for the ground that about philosophical , pedagogical , scientific conclusions given . Also of youth own countries in society social of changes important source and family institute formation for basis as interpretation done Indeed , young people each how in society the future foundation the fact that about historical the experience remember will receive if we this truth today's day to the agenda as an urgent issue comes out Scientists right who noted that " the person vital signs between one series socio-legal qualities separately important have to them have to be young to the individual own subjective rights complete come true release and legal obligations responsibility with done increase , legal from the norms use opportunity gives vital optimal solutions to problems to do tools , that's it including skill and abilities. Legal himself himself protection to do and this of the person enough high level socialization mean holds » .

Legal socialization (Legal socialization) function done increased education system himself study programs of education announcement done reputation - attention and others through adult of those who did not mentality formation because of their crime and of the offense prevention get for very important Mandatory education main the problem is the children the street from the effect keeps, them criminal environment from the effect take throws to ignorance to fall road does not put Plotnikov's to his words according to the students in teaching not but social in education and young generation in the middle strong moral principles and legal behavior in formation problems available ; Less school students own their studies to people useful to be purpose with connect. Theirs important part egocentrism active respectively manifestation does , education to them in life successes does not guarantee wrong thought formed.

In particular, the process of systematic, organized and purposeful pedagogical influence on the mind and will of minors in order to form their mind and will, which we conditionally call criminalistic education and upbringing, criminalistic legal education and upbringing of minors direction is noteworthy. legal consciousness, in which an important place is played, and knowledge of criminal logic. In this we understand the following signs of legal consciousness: the level or level of awareness of rights and obligations, freedoms and, in general, legal interests, as well as their implementation; the idea of law as a phenomenon of value; attitude to the law; the level of awareness of legal protection increases.

The study of the legal consciousness of young people shows that in most cases young people feel vulnerable in difficult life situations precisely because of insufficient legal education. In particular, this explains the feeling of self-doubt on the part of teenagers . In this regard, it is of great importance to develop the interest of minors in the study of jurisprudence. Sociologists found a connection between the interest in reading and the student's sense of justice: "... the more a teenager likes to read , the more he is responsible for the crimes of his peers without considering any circumstances if he gives a negative assessment, he justifies them less. A comparison of the legal consciousness of juvenile delinquents and law-abiding teenagers shows that the criminal law necessary for the legal

behavior of both categories of juveniles the total amount of knowledge is much higher. It is appropriate to evaluate this process not as a set of rules of behavior established once and for all by legislation, the legislator, but as a complex dynamic system that requires constant correction due to the complexity of changing social relations .

It is desirable to create a system of "Criminological education and training", more precisely, a legal education system in the minds of young adults , in which the basics of criminological knowledge (especially becoming a victim of crime) will be inculcated, and the skills of minors will be formed based on a single concept. A comprehensive program, development of methodical recommendations for teachers on the prevention of offenses among students (including prevention of victimization, methods of self-defense against various criminal attacks), as well as delinquent children work with; training should form the basis of this educational system. Since the fundamental beginning of the proposed system for ensuring the criminological stability of minors in the context of criminal threat is a suitable concept, it is necessary to focus on the primary or initial ideas that should be scientifically developed and developed in the future.

One of the most complicated legal situations is the case of necessary defense or extreme necessity, where even adults have to prove the legality of their actions in court without success. It seems that the use of the right of necessary self-defense, including not only self-defense, but also the defense of another person, is prevented, first of all, by the fact that the victim is not morally ready (for example, to hit a person). , and even with a knife or some kind of weapon, especially to shoot a person); secondly, uncertainty about the legality of their actions. In our opinion, it is promising to organize legal education in a general educational institution based on the principle of harmonizing the interests of the community of teachers and parents, on the basis of comprehensive planning. Latin from the language translation made " complex " *connection , combination said the meaning means*. Planned the work - thorough thought out and organize done education object deep to know based on different different official respectively mutually connected and to the content suitable coming events done increase own into takes.

This of work organization and stability , efficiency and in general , adult of those who did not criminal safety regional system situation provide for appropriate monitoring control " observed of the object situation regularly measure system as " necessary , that is crime his own mutually depending on , collection , re work and criminological information known stable criteria according to assessment " . This research In the context of our monitoring - criminal safety object as determined to the object information (educational , educational and prophylactic and others) of influence situation systematic observation , in it shown characteristics , trends let's find out . being observed in the facility and them defined criteria according to evaluation and being studied of the object known one future situation prophecy to do directed without interpretation We did it. Because it 's an adult not enough with working organizations The moral-legal or legal consciousness of minors, who consider it the basis of criminological stability, is interested in. Regular measurement of his condition should be carried out according to certain criteria.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, there are special road maps for improving the legal literacy of young people in the system of working with minors. These road maps are

implemented in the form of propaganda and meetings in close cooperation with educational institutions, families, and neighborhoods. The main focus of these meetings is Juvenile among young people, lack of control and prevention of delinquency among minors, socially dangerous minor, socially dangerous family, lack of control, neglect, antisocial behavior, etc. 2010 It is carried out on the basis of the legal concepts reflected in the law "On prevention of lack of control and delinquency among minors" adopted on August 12. At the same time, the role of Neighborhoods in establishing control over minors is specially noted. This process was formed on the basis of historical experiences. Because, since ancient times, in our nation, we have a phrase with a deep philosophical meaning: "seven neighborhood parents for one child".

We have proposed some approaches based on the principle of intensification, which guarantee their criminological stability, without special material and financial costs, in order to prevent the wide spread of crime among minors and to ensure the qualitative improvement of their legal socialization. In this regard, it is important to take into account the rules developed by us in relation to the object of criminological security, proposed by us in the second paragraph of the second chapter, when developing the methods of forming the criminological stability of a minor.

Conclusion: A minor and his microenvironment as an object of the criminological security system play a decisive role in establishing external relations in which protective elements (measures) are manifested, as a result of which the object's internal security and external protection are ensured. Internal security is provided by the criminalistic stability of a minor, which we understand is the ability to anticipate the danger of a criminal threat, to avoid it, to move away from the sources of a criminal threat in the event of a crime. aggression, self-defense by legal means, protection in necessary cases, restoration of violated rights, in particular, it is recommended to implement with the help of law enforcement agencies.

Legal socialization, which forms the legal consciousness of a minor, plays an important role in the formation of such a holistic character of a person, which includes, in particular, the acquisition of criminological knowledge and experience by a minor, ensuring the safety of his life.

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